

ZIKR PROCEDURES IN YASSAVI TARIQA AND ITS EXPRESSION IN FICTION.

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ANNOTATION In this article, special attention is paid to the order of zikr in the Yassaviya order, the ways of their pronunciation, and the expression of zikr in fiction, and its different levels are shown.

Key words: Sufism, zikr, Yassawiya sect, "Hu..hu" zikr, "Bismillah" zikr

Annotation This article shows that in the "Yassavian" sect, special attention is paid to the order of dhikr, the methods of their utterance and the expression of dhikr in fiction and its various degrees

Keywords: mysticism, zikr, Yassavian sect, "Hu..hu" zikri, "Bismillah" zikri

In the 12th century, the first independent sect began to spread among the Turkic peoples in Turkestan, and this sect was the Yassaviya sect. The need to establish the Turkic order arose from the need to spread Islam among the Turkic peoples. Therefore, the ideological sources of Yassaviism are, first of all, the Holy Qur'an and Hadith Sharif. There are some differences in the main principles of etiquette and archon that distinguish this sect from other sects. There are six rules of Yassawism, which are reflected in mystical topics such as Sharia, tariqat, enlightenment, truth, love and love, arif and arif, dervish, faqru-fano, shaykh, pir and guardianship, zikr, khilvat: Know the truth, be absolute. It is necessary to achieve four conditions, such as bravery, literal loyalty, achieving a close rank, not looking for sustenance, deep thinking, space for taxes, time, ikhwan, and rabti sultan. As in other sects of Sufism, the Yassaviya sect has its own strict rules (etiquette). These rules include:

1. A murid should not prefer anyone to his shaykh, he should show absolute surrender.
2. The murid should be so intelligent and perceptive that he can perfectly understand all the signs and symbols of his shayi.
3. The murid must be loyal to all the aqwal (words) and afwal (deeds) of the sheikh, and must be completely mute and independent.
4. It is necessary for the murid to fulfill all the tasks of his murshid (piri) with chustu choloklik (agility) and earnestly, and always agree with him.
5. It is necessary for the murid to be faithful to his word, to be satisfied with his promise, and not to create any doubt in the mind of his murshid.
6. A student must be faithful to his promise and keep his word
7. A murid should always be ready to hand over all his possessions and all his wealth to his sheikh.
8. The murid should be aware of all the secrets of his shaykh and should never imagine his gesture.
9. A murid must consider all the suggestions of his shaykh, make his difficulties easy, and fulfill his advice.
10. For the sake of God, a murid must be ready to sacrifice his wealth and life for the sake of his shaykh, and live as a friend to his friend and an enemy to his enemy.

The founder of the order has such an opinion that "Knowing oneself, not the word of truth" is the main issue. Therefore, he says that a Sufi who seeks the pleasure of this world is not a Sufi, only a person who obeys and prays, preaches honesty and purity, smokes the sorrows of the world, and lives with the concern of the people are real Sufis. . The content of wisdom in the work "Devoni Hikmat" by Ahmed Yassavi, which is famous in the Islamic world, is of great importance for revealing the foundations of this sect. From the beginning to the end of the work, issues such as noble human qualities: simplicity, modesty, love, love, loyalty, truth, justice, superstition and not separating man from man were promoted from a philosophical point of view. And on the contrary, vices such as evil, ignorance, injustice,

ingratitude, and greed are criticized. People with such qualities are called to honesty and piety. According to Alloma, a person should not live in this world relying on rich people, this world will be better than everyone else. That's why people should do good to each other, keep the truth in mind and live without being jealous of other people's wealth:

Know the cradle, this world is beyond all nations,
Don't believe in your possessions, one day it will go away.
Parents, relatives left later, think,
A four-legged chubby horse will come to you one day.
Don't worry about the world, don't talk about yourself
Don't eat a person's property, you will keep it on the poor..

So, based on the blessed hadiths of our Prophet that "poverty is honor" and being faithful to the path of his sect, Khwaja Ahmad Yasavi reached the status of being a leader in "Shahhu gado aning irat wa ikhlosi istani" as written by Hazrat Mir Alisher Navoi. . He praised the great poet Ahmed Yassavi in his work "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" and wrote: "He is a man whose authority is high and famous, whose merit is high and unlimited. . . Imam Yusuf is a companion of Hamadani. . . We want the spirit of great scholars like Ahmed Yassavi to help our nation and its people in the future.

We will consider the types of zikr in the Yassawi sect and their order through the wisdoms in the work "Devoni Hikmat". In almost all of the proverbs, the poet told in a poetic way about the way to recite them in the manner of zikr and yassavit. In the Yassaviya sect, there is mainly "saw zikr" and it is performed in the Jahri method, that is, public zikr. In the zikr of saw, a sound like the sound of a saw is emitted from the throat while keeping the breath in the stomach with the head bowed, that's why zikr in this way is called "zikr saw". The real reason why this tariqa chose open dhikr was the great demand of the people in the place where the tariqat was

formed, the great need for open dhikr. Ahmad Yassavi lived in the people of the people who had a high temper and a tendency to openness. Perhaps this is the reason that the Yassawiya sect spread widely and very quickly among the people.

Qazini gave extensive information about the introduction of the zikr of saw in connection with Khizr in his work. He wrote that one day Khizr came to have a conversation with Ahmed Yassavi as usual. But this time he saw Khoja Ahmad sad and asked the reason, and then his Holiness said: "Sadness has taken over the hearts of our friends, I am worried about how to get rid of it." After that, Khizr, peace be upon him, begins to perform zikrullah, saying "oh-oh", and now this zikr is called "zikr arra" in the Sufi era. Then Khwaja Ahmad repeats this zikr and as a result, "sufferings in the hearts will disappear". With the recommendation of the great pir, this zikr becomes a vird in the Yassaviya series. As we mentioned above, now we turn to "Devoni Hikmat" for the order of dhikr

Saying "Bismillah"

I have scattered gems to the Taliban.
Taking mathematics hard, swallowing blood,
Man, I opened the word "Daftari Soni".

If we pay attention to these verses, it begins with the mention of Allah Almighty, "Bismillah" from Arabic, "in the name of God, the Merciful and Compassionate", it can be seen that even the smallest mentions were used in the Yassawiya tariqa. Yassawism sect spread widely among the people prone to Jazba, and the people's need for zikr (poisonous zikr), which is one of the pillars of Yassawism, also increased. Let's pay attention to another piece of wisdom:

If the animal is mute to the creature,
The people of the world are praying for that slave.
If he recites the zikr, his heart swells and his insides burn,
When he says "Huh...Huh", countless sparks fly, friends

This wisdom is about the servant's need for God, and whoever mentions Khaliq, that is, Allah Almighty, says, "Huh... Pay attention with the dhikr of "Hu", if he remembers with this dhikr, Allah the Exalted says that innumerable light (sparks) will fly from the burning heart of the person who recites the dhikr. "Huh.... "Hu" zikr is one of the most meritorious zikrs among the zikrs, the author used it skillfully in fiction and was able to enliven his thoughts in a wonderful way.

Not God, let the jinn pour out the herbs.
When you say "Hu", your butts will flash like lightning.
Let your stomach burst, your lungs swell and melt,
Until you do your indispensable service.

The one who stepped on this path died.
Reciting the zikr will blow your heart,
Andin then opened the door after looking at John.
Until he does his service, which cannot be opened.

In these quatrains it is also mentioned about dhikr, but who will teach you how to dhikr? Of course, the pir, that is, the sheikh, teaches. The author wants to say that it is difficult to recite and learn both the "Hu" zikr and the "Zikri qalb" without breaking the heart.

Ahmad Yassavi mentioned in his hikmats the type of zikr known as "heavenly dance" and how it appeared, pay attention;

The Maloiks cried and talked for a day,
The dance ran to hit the sky,
Meraj saw the right Mustafa,
Now I want to dance and dance.

Haq Mustafa fainted because of Mi'raj,
Jibril is right, Mustafa is happy,
Subhan Izim taught zikr with power.
If I am an Ummah, I will remember the zikr.

As we can see in this murabba, during the days of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) when he ascended to Miraj, they saw the "zikr samo" and wanted to learn this zikr from them, and Jibril (a.s.) was responsible for teaching the zikr to our prophet. s) is ordered. In this way, the sheikhs indicate that the "sky of remembrance" has appeared. About the zikr in the following verses, the shaykh has very impressively described its characteristics in a poetic way:

If I say "Kul huwallah" and "Subhanallah"
Biru, I'm going, can I see your sister?
If I make you miss me from head to toe,
Biru, I'm going, can I see your sister?

The dhikrs in these verses are also called among the greatest dhikrs by the mashaikhs, these two dhikrs "Qul huwallah" and "Subhanallah" are also obligatory in the prayer of the five places of prayer, and therefore the sheikhs emphasize that these dhikrs are among the greatest dhikrs. The metaphor "Biru Borim" in the second verse is a reference to Allah Ta'ala.

Allah-Allah, Subhanallah, where shall I go?
My books don't fit on the ground, who should I tell?
Sattar Lord, if I am guilty,
I'm stuck in the middle of the black earth.

His hair and beard flowed well, take heart,
If I go in the morning, I'm either a puchuk or a saro,
Who said "Alastu bi Rabbukum?" so far
I don't know why I'm so happy.

The arrow of strangeness hit me, my head froze,
Don't forget, life was wasted with carelessness,
My unbelieving ego swallowed me up.
I'm sorry, I didn't go with my face.

Dhikrs such as "Allah-Allah" and "Subhanallah" in the first verse are among the most used dhikrs in Yassawiya tariqa. The hope of the Rish is one of the most important aspects of this sect.

You mouthed the slave saying "Laa ilaha illallah".
A green bird is flying.

You loved me with full wings,
After flying, Arshdin landed on Arshka.

Khul Khoja Ahmed, poor and strange, was surprised,
Saying "Laa illaha illallah"
Remembering the truth to the heart,
You can see the soul bird in the meadow.

As we mentioned above, the dhikr "Laa illaha illallah" is considered the greatest dhikr, and this dhikr was most often used by Khwaja Ahmed Yassavi. We can show "Devoni Hikmat" as a proof of this.

O lover, hard work in this world,
Enjoy the hardships you have endured,

Hit the ground where the "Hu" conversation was built,
Urgan will find his lover, friends.

The reward of these paths is sorrow, labor,
The pleasure of suffering from labor
In the mornings, the country is forced to see,
"Hoo-Hoo" and this world will pass, my friends.

This hikmat also uses the zikr "Hu", and the combination "Hu suhbatin" in the third verse also refers to the "zikrullah" zikr meetings. The sheikh wants to say through wisdom that a servant who remembers and remembers Allah may walk with sorrow in this world, but when he sees the beauty of the Creator in the real world, he will forget all his troubles. We will give examples of such wisdom:

If the animal is mute to the creature,

The people of the world love that slave, friends,
If he recites the zikr, his heart swells and his insides burn,
When he says "Huh...Huh", countless sparks fly, friends.

The nightingale wanders through Boston, the present epic,
Inevitable summers and winters,
Those who serve will be happy on these roads,
Fly and fly to the air, friends.

Conclusion, "Devoni Hikmat" f.f.d. Nodirkhan Hasanov and Ph.D. The collection of Khoja Ahmed Yassavi "Umring yeldek otaro" published by Ibrahim Haqqullar in 2022 formed the basis of our work, we used this source more in the analysis of wisdom. It is interesting that in the wisdoms of this collection the word "zikr" is used more than five hundred times, that is, "remember if you are zikr", "Muhammad who mentioned zikr", "zikr like the key to heaven", it can be seen that the place of zikr was special in the Yassawiya tariqa.

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